

**MATERIALS OF THE GENERAL PLAN OF KISHINEV AS OF YEAR 1947,
FROM THE ARCHIVES IN THE LIBRARY OF THE UNION
OF ARCHITECTS OF MOLDOVA**

*Materialele Planului General al Chișinăului, păstrate în biblioteca
Uniunii Arhitecților din Republica Moldova*

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The book containing the list of the activities of the Union of Architects of Moldova was published in 1947. According to the chapter “Overview of the work of Soviet architects of the MSSR” the General Reconstruction Plan of Kishinev was presented by Academician A. V. Shchusev.

The Council organized a public presentation of the General plan for the reconstruction of the Kishinev (by Academician A. V. Shchusev). The event was also attended by representatives from various institutions and city organizations. The meeting of the leading Moscow architects took place at the Union of Architects of Moldova.

A lecture on Soviet architecture was given to the members of the UAM by Academician A. V. Shchusev. Both the 800th Moscow anniversary exhibition and the A.V. Shchusev’s report presentation were held in the Party Office.

“The Planning and Reconstruction of City Centers in the USSR” presentation was given by Fellow Correspondent of the Academy of Architecture V.V. Baburov. (Victor Veniaminovich Baburov is a renowned architect and urban planner. He participated in the reconstruction project of Moscow in 1932 and its suburban area in 1934. He is known as one of the authors of the “Fundamentals of Urban Planning” (1951) guide for architectural universities, as well as for a large number of publications on this topic.) The book published in 1947 also includes a chapter written by Robert Kurtz. The architect comprehensively discusses the General Plan of Kishinev by Academician A.V. Shchusev.

Info related to the General Plan of Kishinev, submitted by A.V. Shchusev, is kept at the Shchusev House-Museum. Materials include original drawings and perspectives, created by Academician A.V. Shchusev both on his own and together with the team.

The album containing photographs of the presented works was handed over to the library of the Union of Architects to provide the members with an opportunity to carefully study the project.

The album has dimensions of 520 by 360 mm and a thickness of 55 mm. The cover is wrapped in dark gray calico, and the number “918” is written in the upper right corner. The album contains 25 sheets, and 40 photographs are pasted on 22 of them. Additionally, there is one sheet with a drawing enclosed in the album.

Based on the works presented in the album, we can assess the range of materials submitted, as well as identify the architects who participated in this project under A.V. Shchusev’s guidance.

Official stamp: “Architectural workshops of the committee for architecture affairs under the council of ministers of the USSR. Project supervisor and author: academician A.V. Shchusev.”

Page 1. Two images: General plan of Kishinev (photo of the model) and “Plan of the area adjacent to Kishinev.” The planning project was developed by architect Z.K. Rostkovskaya with the participation of architect I.I. Novikov.

Page 2. “Base plan of Kishinev.” Developed by architect Z.K. Rostkovskaya-Yashina with the participation of architect I.I. Novikov.

Page 3. Two drawings: “Kishinev station area layout” developed with the participation of architects Z.K. Rostkovskaya and N.T. Bogomolova. “Layout of the center of Kishinev” developed with the participation of architects Z.K. Rostkovskaya and Yakovleva.

Page 4. Two drawings: Unidentified street layouts (Lenin Street).

Page 5. Perspective view of Kishinev. Designed by architect A. P. Agafonov.

Page 6. “Kishinev, Lenin Street.”

Page 7. Two drawings: “Development project of Rishkanovskaya Hill in Kishinev” and “Layout of Rishkanovskaya Hill in Kishinev,” both developed by architect Turchiniov, along with a perspective view of the two presented drawings.

Page 8. Two views of the center of Kishinev with the Government House.

Page 9. “Government House in Kishinev, main facade.” With the participation of architect E.S. Sorokina.

Page 10. “Palace of the Government of the Moldavian SSR.” With the participation of architect A.P. Agafonov.

Page 11. “Government House” Two facades. With the participation of architect E.S. Sorokina.

Page 12. “Government House. Cross-section” With the participation of architect E.S. Sorokina. “Interior” with the signature of A.V. Shchusev.

Page 13. “Government House. Plans of three floors.” With the participation of architect E. S. Sorokina.

Page 14. Theater in Kishinev, market in Kishinev. Two perspectives.

Page 15. Perspective view of a building.

Page 16. Perspective view of a university building.

Page 17. University building. Two images: facade and section.

Page 18. University building. Four plans.

Page 19. Perspective view of the center of Kishinev in the area of Sadovaya Street. Variant 1.

Page 20. Perspective view of the center of Kishinev in the area of Sadovaya Street. Variant 2.

Page 21. Views of the Mazarakievskaya Church. Two images.

Page 22. Perspective view.

Page 23. “Reconstruction of a residential building (Swiss Hotel).” “Bridge over the Kishinev Canal.”

The most marvelous discovery in the album was a sheet of dense yellowed paper with a drawing made in colored pencils. The size of the sheet is 38 cm by 29.5 cm.

It depicts the perspective view. of the central part of Kishinev taken from a bird’s-eye view, from the side of Gogol Street (Bănulescu-Bodoni Street). The Arch of Triumph, Lenin, Pushkin and Gogol Streets, as well as the planned Government House are easy to recognize.

Taking into account the fact that A.V. Shchusev personally executed some of the works presented in the album, it is reasonable to assume that this sketch was also created by his

hand. A qualified expertise can verify this hypothesis. However, it is undeniable that the discovered sketch is part of Shchusev's project, allowing us to better comprehend the author's concept and the process of working on the project.

Acquainting ourselves with the list of architects who participated in the development of the General Plan can help us find new materials about this significant event in the history of Kishinev.